

Studies in Potential Amoebicides. Part XVI*—Synthesis of Some Quinaldinyl and Bi-quinolypropane Derivatives and Their Reduction Products

S. C. Misra and S. P. Popli

Synthesis of a number of 2-aryl-1, 3-bi-2'-quinolypropanes, piperidino-, and morpholino-ethylquinolines as well as their reduction products as possible antiamoebic agents is described.

It has been suggested by Dhar and coworkers¹ that the similar biological response of such widely different molecular species as emetine and conessine, in the treatment of systemic amoebiasis, is mediated by two-point hydrogen bonding between the component nitrogen atoms of these two drug molecules with appropriate bioreceptors. On this basis, a variety of compounds with two suitably substituted nitrogen atoms, placed appropriately apart, have been synthesised and reported from this laboratory^{1,2}. Some of these compounds have been shown to possess pronounced antiamoebic activity in experimental amoebiasis of rats³.

In pursuance of our search for more effective and specific amoebicides, several 2-aryl-1,3-bi-2'-quinolypropanes (I; R=H or OMe; R'=substituted phenyl), 2- β -piperidino- and morpholino-ethylquinolines (II; R=H or OMe; NR₁R₂=piperidino or morpholino moiety), as well as their reduction products, have now been prepared and are reported in the present communication.

2-Phenyl-1, 3-bi-2'-quinolypropane was prepared by a modified procedure of Skidmore and Tidd⁴ involving condensation of suitable quinaldines with appropriate 2-styrylquinolines, the use of hydrochloric acid in place of zinc chloride having been found to improve the yields of the bi-quinolypropanes. These on reduction with sodium and amyl alcohol gave the corresponding bi-2'-(1', 2', 3', 4'-tetrahydroquinoly)-propanes. The inherent reactivity of the 2-methyl group in the quinaldines was utilised also for the preparation of Mannich bases of the type (II). The latter were reduced catalytically in presence of PtO₂ in *N*-HCl to the corresponding 1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinoline derivatives.

The compounds reported in this communication are being tested as possible amoebicides in the Microbiology Division of this Institute and their findings will be reported separately.

*Part XV. Gopalchhari and Dhar, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.* (in press)

1. Mahboob and Dhar, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1955, 14B, 1; Popli and Dhar, *ibid.*, 1960, 19C, 208.

2. Popli, *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1956, 15C, 276; Paul and Anand, *ibid.*, 1958, 17B, 219; Agarwal and Paul, *ibid.*, 1961, 20C, 147.

3. Singh and Miss Sharma, Proc. Symposium on Chemotherapy, Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow, 1959, p. 157; Miss Saxena and Singh, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1960, 19C, 293.

4. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 1641.

EXPERIMENTAL

1-p-Hydroxyphenyl-2,2'-quinolyethanol.—A mixture of *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde (6.4 g.), benzoic acid (0.5 g.) and quinaldine (7.5 ml) was kept at 50° for 100 hrs. The precipitate was separated, washed with light petroleum (b. p. 60-80°) and crystallised from ethanol to yield colorless needles, m. p. 265°, yield 40%. This and other quinolyethanols, prepared similarly, are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I
1-Substituted phenyl-2,2'-quinolyethanols.

Sl. No.	R.	R'.	M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen	
					Found.	Reqd.
424**	H	H	131°	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ ON	5.32	5.60
425	H	<i>o</i> -OH	212°	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₂ N	5.32	5.28
426	H	<i>p</i> -OH	265°	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₂ N	5.19	5.28
427	H	<i>o</i> -Cl	130°	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ONCl	4.78	4.94
428	H	<i>p</i> -OMe	128°	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₂ N	4.82	5.00

*Serial numbers continued from Part XV (loc. cit.)

**All compounds except those marked thus are new.

2-p-Hydroxystyrylquinoline.—The foregoing quinolyethanol (10 g.) was treated with acetic anhydride (100 ml) according to Benrath³ to obtain *2-p*-acetoxystrylquinoline as glistening needles, m. p. 133°, in a quantitative yield. This on being refluxed with aqueous 10% NaOH solution for 2 hrs. gave *2-p*-hydroxystyrylquinoline, m. p. 258°; hydrochloride, m. p. 298°. The other styrylquinolines were prepared likewise and are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II
2-Styrylquinolines

Sl. No.	R.	R'.	Base.	H.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.		M.P.	Hydrochloride	
						Found.	Reqd.		Found.	Reqd.
429**	H	H		98°	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N	6.05	6.06	..	..	..
430	H	<i>o</i> -OAc		92°	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ O ₂ N	4.88	4.84	115°	4.28	4.30
431**	H	<i>p</i> -QH		258°	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N	5.58	5.60	298°	4.93	4.94
432	H	<i>p</i> -OAc		133°	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ O ₂ N	4.62	4.84	120°	3.97	4.30
433	H	<i>o</i> -Cl		80°	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ NCl	5.01	5.27	250°	4.42	4.63
434**	H	<i>p</i> -OMe		129°	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ ON	5.19	5.36	207°	4.53	4.71
435	H	<i>p</i> -N ₃ Me ₂		182°	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₃	10.25	10.20	233°	8.09	8.09

2-p-Hydroxyphenyl-1,3-bi-2'-quinolylpropane.—*2-p*-Hydroxystyrylquinoline hydrochloride (5.0 g.) and quinaldine (7.1 ml) were heated together at 135° for 5 hrs. The

product was dissolved in HCl (2*N*, 3 × 80 ml), and dilute NaOH solution added to it gradually till it was just acid to litmus. The precipitate was filtered and crystallised from ethanol, m. p. 210°; yield 80%; hydrochloride, m. p. 190° (ethanol). The bi-quinolypropanes now prepared are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III
2-Aryl-1,3-bi-2'-quinolypropanes.

Sl. No.	Base.			Formula.	% Nitrogen		Dihydrochloride		
	R.	R'.	M.P.		Found.	Reqd.	M.P.	Found.	Reqd.
436	OCH ₃	H	..	C ₂₉ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₂	..	..	210°	5.79	5.53
437	H ⁺ *	H	92°	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ N ₂	7.40	7.50	156°	6.00	6.26
438	H	<i>o</i> -OH	..	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ ON ₂	..	..	188°	5.67	6.04
439	H	<i>p</i> -OH	210°	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ ON ₂	7.10	7.18	190°	6.13	6.04
440	H	<i>o</i> -Cl	100°	C ₂₇ H ₂₁ N ₂ Cl	6.60	6.85	..	..	..
441	H	<i>p</i> -OMe	..	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ ON ₂	..	..	122°	5.77	5.87
442	H	<i>p</i> NMe ₂	..	C ₂₉ H ₂₇ N ₃	..	..	202°	6.75	6.57

2-*p*-Hydroxyphenyl-1,3-bi-2'-(1', 2', 3', 4'-tetrahydroquinolyl)propane.—The above bi-quinolypropane (2.0 g.) was dissolved in boiling amylⁿ alcohol (30 ml), and sodium (6.0 g.) was added to it gradually (2 hrs.). The reaction mixture was refluxed for further 2 hrs., the product cooled, diluted with water, and steam-distilled till all the amyl alcohol passed over. The residue was extracted with ether and the ether extract dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The solvent was then removed and the base converted into the hydrochloride, m. p. 268°. The other bi-quinolypropanes were reduced in the same manner and are recorded in Table IV.

TABLE IV
2-Aryl-1,3-bi-2'-(1',2',3',4'-tetrahydroquinolyl)propanes.

Sl. No.	R.	R'.	Formula.	M.P.	% Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.
443	H	H	C ₂₇ H ₃₀ N ₂ ·2 HCl	230°	5.93	6.15
444	H	<i>o</i> -OH	C ₂₇ H ₃₀ ON ₂ ·2 HCl	262°	5.62	5.95
445	H	<i>p</i> -OH	C ₂₇ H ₃₀ ON ₂ ·2 HCl	268°	6.06	5.95
446*	H	<i>o</i> -Cl	C ₂₇ H ₂₉ N ₂ Cl ₂ ·2 HCl	245°	5.83	5.72
447	H	<i>p</i> -OMe	C ₂₈ H ₃₂ ON ₂ ·2 HCl	220°	5.93	5.77
448	H	<i>p</i> -NMe ₂	C ₂₉ H ₃₃ N ₃ ·2 HCl	208°	8.06	8.40

*Dipicrate, m. p. 215° (Found: N, 12.90. C₃₆H₃₃O₁₄N₈ Cl requires N, 12.80%).

2-β-Piperidinoethyl-6-methoxyquinoline (Sl. No. 449).—Formalin (40%, 3 ml) was condensed with piperidine (3.4 g.) and 6-methoxyquinaldine hydrochloride (4.2 g.) according to the procedure of Kermack and Muir⁵ and *2-β-piperidinoethyl-6-methoxyquinoline* so obtained was converted into the corresponding picrate which was crystallised from acetone, m.p. 175°; yield 70% (Found: N, 14.13. C₂₃H₂₅O₈N₅ requires N, 14.03%).

2-β-Piperidinoethyl-6-methoxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinoline (Sl. No. 450).—The above Mannich base (2.0 g.) was dissolved in *N*-HCl (50 ml) and hydrogenated at 60 lbs/p.s.i., for 20 hrs. in presence of PtO₂ (100 mg.). The solution was then made alkaline (NaOH) and extracted with ether. The solvent was removed and the base distilled, b.p. 245°/8 mm. (bath temp.) (Found: N, 10.80. C₁₇H₂₆ON₂ requires, N, 10.22%).

2-β-Piperidinoethyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinoline (Sl. No. 451) was prepared in a similar manner from *2-β-piperidino-ethylquinoline*.⁶ It was converted into its picrate, m.p. 171° (ethanol). (Found: N, 14.76. C₂₂H₂₇O₇N₅ requires N, 14.80%).

2-β-Morpholinoethylquinoline (Sl. No. 452) was prepared from morpholine, quinaldine hydrochloride and formaldehyde (40%) in 75% yield. The oily product was converted into the corresponding picrate, in benzene solution, which recrystallised readily from ethanol, m.p. 194° (Found: N, 14.65. C₂₁H₂₁O₈N₅ requires N, 14.86%).

2-β-Morpholinoethyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinoline (Sl. No. 453).—The above base was dissolved in *N*-HCl and reduced in an atmosphere of hydrogen at 60 lbs/p.s.i. in presence of PtO₂. The reduction product, which was obtained in a quantitative yield, was converted into the corresponding picrate and crystallised from acetone, m.p. 165°. (Found: N, 14.95. C₂₁H₂₅O₈N₅ requires N, 14.73%).

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DIVISION OF MEDICINAL CHEMISTRY,
CENTRAL DRUG RESEARCH INSTITUTE,
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